

FOREIGN MODERN EXPERIENCE OF MANAGING PRECARIOUS EMPLOYMENT

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Abstract: Growth of informal employment in the world significantly changes the traditional models of employment on permanent working places, and the number of precarious workers is growing. As a result, the requirements of the decent employment concept of the International Labor Organization are violated. The article describes modern forms of precarious employment and analyzes approaches to its assessment.

Keywords: precarisation, employment flexibility, precariat, sustainable employment, precarious employment

Annotatsiya. Dunyoda norasmiy bandlik darajasining o‘sishi xodimlarning doimiy ish joyida ish bilan ta’minlanishining an’anaviy shakllarini sezilarli darajada o‘zgartirmoqda va prekariatlar (beqaror ish bilan band bo‘lganlar) soni ortib bormoqda. Natijada Xalqaro mehnat tashkilotining munosib bandlik konsepsiyasi talablari buzilmoqda. Maqolada beqaror ish bilan bandlikning zamonaviy shakllari tavsiflangan hamda uni baholashga yondashuvlar tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: prekarizatsiya, egiluvchan bandlik, prekariat (beqaror ish bilan band aholi), barqaror bandlik, beqaror ish bilan bandlik.

Аннотация: Увеличение уровня неформальной занятости в мире значительно меняет традиционные модели занятости наемных работников на постоянном рабочем месте, и количество прекариатов растет. В результате нарушаются требования концепции достойной занятости Международной

Организации Труда. В статье описываются современные формы прекаризованной занятости населения и анализируются подходы к ее оценке.

Ключевые слова: прекаризация, гибкость занятости, прекариат, устойчивая занятость, прекаризация занятости населения.

Introduction.

Despite a number of efforts to ensure decent working conditions and adequate employment in the world, unsustainable employment is becoming an increasingly serious social problem. According to the ILO, “In 2019, a large proportion of the world’s 3.3 billion people in paid employment have been employed in jobs that do not provide decent working conditions or adequate income. Especially in low- and middle-income countries, 1.4 billion people worked in informal, vulnerable conditions”[1]. Today special attention is paid to the implementation of appropriate measures in targeted regulation of labor market liberalization, increasing attention to social guarantees in social-labor relations and in accordance with the requirements of the International Labor Organization's Concept of Decent Work.

The world is conducting extensive researches aimed at solving the problems of social and labor relations of precarious employment. The researches include the liberalization of the labor market in the context of labor mobility and migration, solving problems of social guarantees and social-labor relations as a whole system, a special attention is paid to improving the methodology for determining informal employment and development of non-standard forms of employment.

In Uzbekistan, especially in recent years, issues such as improving the quality of life, providing permanent employment, creating new jobs are becoming a priority. “The task of improving the living standards and quality of life in the regions, in particular poverty reduction is in many ways directly related to the creation of new and sustainable jobs by increasing the competitiveness of all sectors and sectors of the economy and creating fundamental conditions for entrepreneurship”[2]. In addressing

these challenges, reducing the level of precarious employment on the basis of target parameters of labor market regulation, increase the level of non-standard forms of employment, it is expedient to deepen research in such areas as substantiation of income indicators based on the factors influencing income instability.

Methods.

Theoretical and methodological basis of precarious employment, distribution of people into social strata, non-standard types of employment in the labor market without certain social protection and legal guarantees, changed informal forms of employment and the scientific basis of their impact on social and labor relations studied by foreign scientists: Robert Castel, Gay Standing, Pierre Bourdieu, C. Paugam, R.D. Hepp, B.L. Nugarten, A. Kollberg and others.

Scientific approaches of non-standard employment problems, some modern types and forms of precarious employment have been presented by scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States as V.N. Bobkov, O.V. Veredyuk, V.E. Gimpelson, U.G. Odegov, Z.T. Golenkova, U.V. Goliusova, E.A. Grishinina, N.V. Osipova, N.J. Alshanova and others.

Social and labor relations in Uzbekistan - the formation and development of the labor market, regulation of employment and labor migration, reducing unemployment and theoretical and practical aspects of creating new jobs are found its expression in scientific works of K.Kh. Abdurakhmanov, D.N. Rahimova, N.K. Zokirova, B.H. Umurzakov, N.H. Rakhimova, Z.Y. Khudoiberdiev, N.U. Arabov and others.

The British economist G.Standing describes the nature of the category of precariat as follows: “Many of what we call precariat have never seen their employer, have no idea how many employees the employer has in their hands, and how many employees it plans to hire in the future. Precariat cannot be included in the middle class because it does not have a stable salary, does not correspond to the status of the middle class, and is not entitled to guaranteed benefits for them”.[3]

The French scientist P. Bourdieu made a great contribution to the analysis of the state of precariat. He describes the precariat as an unstable, defenseless, marginal category of the population (from the Latin word "margo" - "edge"), is isolated from society.[4]

Therefore, Robert Castel believes that the main reason for the emergence of precarisation is the destruction of the industrial order of labor organization and the social system of society.

However, the collective protection system of the twentieth century (labor law, social insurance system, the social state that regulates these structures) served as a kind of "airbag" in the event of social threats[5].

Serge Paugam sees such separation of the able-bodied population as a mechanism that accelerates precarisation. It is this mechanism that turns the relatively low-skilled, inexperienced and intolerant part of the able-bodied population into precariat[6].

Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Economics K. Abdurahmanov says that the reason for the formation of precarisation is "The wide range of non-standard employment is the result of structural changes in the production of goods and services, the emergence of new forms of production relations in labor and entrepreneurship in a situation of increasing labor market flexibility"[7].

Dissertation research used systematic analysis, grouping, logical thinking, complex evaluation, logical and comparative analysis, statistical and econometric modeling, prospective forecasting methods.

Results.

According to the data of the International Labor Organization, the standard labor relations show that they do not accurately represent the real situation in the labor market: currently only a quarter of wage workers are covered by them. Unstable employment is also widespread in the developed countries of the world. According to the International Labor Organization, today there are 2 billion people in the world.

person (61.0% of the working-age population) has an unstable job. Currently, only 48.0% of women are employed. The youth unemployment rate has reached 20.0%.

Increased sociological research on the reasons why working population performs work on the basis of unstable employment, including 80.0% of respondents with such a job in the USA - hope to have a permanent job, 80.0% of respondents in Europe - gaining experience, in Japan 50.0% of the respondents stated that it is acceptable to balance work and personal life. That is, their employment in this way indicates that it does not contradict their labor rights. (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Types of employment in the world (% of total employment)¹

However, in the report of the International Labor Organization "Non-standard employment in the world: keeping in mind the challenges, defining the perspective", non-standard forms of employment (NSFE), including temporary, part-time employment, temporary borrowed work, Concern is expressed that the scope of subcontracting, hidden labor relations is expanding.

The report warns that non-standard workplaces provide workers with access to the labor market, but that, while achieving a degree of flexibility between employers and employees, deprives labor of job security. Currently, the difference between the wages of employees working in permanent and temporary jobs is 30%.

¹ Information from the International Labor Organization // <http://www.ilo.org>
WWW.HUMOSCIENCE.COM

The scale of unstable employment in the world is also shown by the fact that the Swiss agency "Adecco" uses the labor of 700,000 temporary employees, and the Japanese agency "Pasona" gives 250,000 people a day to work on short-term contracts.².

In industrialized countries, work under the conditions of "extremely short working hours" or "on-call work", including "zero labor contracts" (no minimum working hours guaranteed), is taking on the characteristics of casual employment in developing countries. For example, in the UK, 2.5% of employees have "zero employment contracts", and in the US, 10.0% of employees work on call or have an unstable schedule.

In EU countries, between 1984 and 2015, temporary employment increased from 8.0% to 14.0% of all employment, and part-time employment increased from 12.0% to 17.0%.

Currently, Austria, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Luxembourg, Austria, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Luxembourg - in education and social sectors, Greece, Portugal, Italy, France, Spain, Latvia, Switzerland, Belgium, Spain - in agriculture and forestry, In Estonia and Ireland, casual employment in the construction sector dominates over formal employment.

Unstable employment has become a feature even in Japan, which has a tradition of lifelong employment. Currently, a third of the employed in this country are working in a temporary workplace³.

At the same time, the informal sector also performs some important social and economic functions. First, it provides an opportunity for workers who cannot find work in the formal sector to work, even if it is unstable. In this way, it helps to earn income

² Almeida, Rita and Pedro Carneiro. Enforcement of Labor Regulation and Firm Size // Journal of Comparative Economics. 37 (2009): - P.28-46.

³ Сургуладзе В.Ш. Прекариат – новый революционный класс информационной эпохи: глобальная трансформация рынка труда и её социально-экономические и политические последствия // <https://aftershock.news/?q=node/690885&full>

of socially unprotected population categories. Second, the informal sector is often the first step for entrepreneurs to start their own businesses.

But the social problems of precarious employment - the loss of tax revenues, the reduction of labor productivity and the deprivation of social security - far outweigh those opportunities mentioned above. Therefore, regulation of unstable employment is one of the important tasks in the socio-economic policy of the state.

State regulation of precarious employment in the European Union is based on four main principles:

1. Preventive measures. They include the simplification of procedures for the establishment of their businesses by entrepreneurs, the reduction of costs for this, the removal of obstacles to the official declaration of their activities.

2. Penalties. It is aimed at strengthening control functions and aims to apply appropriate sanctions to those who benefit from clandestine labor activities. Also, measures will be taken to protect those who have been dismissed in cooperation with relevant tax and law-enforcement bodies and labor inspectorates.

3. Production to combat fraud in the social network and trade in informal employment within transnational production activities by EU member states.

4. The informal employment of the public helps to increase the solidarity work, production, and working capacity of workers.

Discussion.

Labor legislation plays a key role in ensuring basic labor rights - setting the procedure for hiring and firing employees, establishing minimum wages, creating opportunities to obtain formal jobs, approving employment programs, and protecting the unemployed. In particular, the political reforms carried out in the labor market will help the employees to give up working in the informal sector, and the employment programs will serve to prepare the employees to increase their work in the formal sector.

According to the Union of Industrial Enterprises of the European Community (UNICE), the main problem in the regulation of labor legislation in the EU member states is to achieve proportionality - on the one hand, the flexibility of legal norms, and on the other hand, ensuring the social protection of employees. The priority is to create enough jobs in the community. However, this can only be achieved if the labor market is flexible. But in such circumstances, the issue of social security of employees remains open.

For example, German labor law pays special attention to the issue of labor protection. General, social, technical and medical protection of labor are its components. It can be called a beneficial factor of employment formalization.

In France, the change of the labor law in 2016 caused serious protests. These changes included the ability to extend the work week to 45 hours with the approval of local unions while maintaining the 35-hour work week, as well as easing the procedures for reducing wages and laying off employees.

In the fight against informal employment in EU member states, a close cooperation has been established between various state institutions - labor inspectorates, social security and tax authorities. The swiftness and openness of the legal system is helpful in notifying authorities of informal employment problems, such as illegal dismissals.

In developed countries, tax policy is the main tool in the fight against informal employment. This is mainly done in two ways. The first is to reduce payroll taxes and social security contributions and other taxes on businesses and/or employees. The second - direct fiscal measures - is to attract non-taxpaying employees to fulfill their tax obligations by placing the tax liability on the employer.

Since the second half of the 1990s, a number of countries forming a market economy have implemented tax reforms aimed at reducing the amount of taxes for labor resources, especially for employees with low and low wages. Many of these countries have introduced tax breaks for specific categories of employees. (Table 1)

For example, in Belgium and France, tax cuts for low-wage workers have encouraged them to formalize their activities. In Slovakia, the progressive income tax was abolished and the introduction of a single tax rate of 19.0% for individuals and legal entities served to formalize the labor relations of those engaged in informal labor activities. Administrative measures are mainly aimed at ensuring the implementation of laws. It is aimed at increasing the capacity of organizations responsible for this issue, and strengthening the penalties for violations. At the same time, administrative measures also involve informing the public about the prospects for businesses and individuals depending on whether they choose the formal or informal sector.

Table 1**Tax benefits for employees in foreign countries**

Countries	Employment category	Tax benefits
Austria, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Holland, Spain, Turkey	Individuals	Determination of the highest rates of regressive social payments in the income tax system. But in a number of cases, they are applied to certain types of payments and retain their progressive nature along with income tax.
Czech Republic, Greece and Portugal	Self employed	Determining a lower rate of social payments compared to those of employees of enterprises

Hungary and Spain	Self employed	Special simplified tax procedure
A number of countries that are members of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development	For individuals	Full exemption from double taxation of profits distributed as dividends

France, Belgium and the Netherlands	Persons engaged in unregistered labor activities (domestic servants, those engaged in furnishing and repairing houses and apartments)	Tax benefits
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Conclusion.

If the main conditions regulating the economic sector are determined by the tax policy, business environment and labor market regulation, a lot depends on the institutions working in this direction. For example, the effectiveness of medical care and pension provision determines the interest of working in the official sector, while fulfilling the appropriate social payments for these areas. At the same time, the effectiveness of law enforcement institutions serves to successfully fight against informal economic activity.

Regulation of business activity covers aspects such as registration of enterprises, legal procedures, and the general business environment. It plays a decisive role in the choice of the formal or informal sector by economic entities. For example, the ease of registration and licensing of enterprises will undoubtedly encourage them to enter the formal sector. At the same time, the protection of the assets of enterprises by the state, the fair resolution of emerging problems will also be an incentive for the implementation of official economic activities⁴.

The world has accumulated positive experiences on the implementation of labor activities in the order of unstable employment. For example, the Netherlands leads the world in the number of part-time employees. Almost half of all employed people here (65.0% of women and 28.0% of men) work part-time. Most importantly, it is widely used in all sectors of the economy, not limited to certain types of work. Women are especially happy with such work.

In the Netherlands, in 2000, a special law on the regulation of working hours was adopted. It provides guarantees for combining employment with caring for relatives. In particular, employees may request the employer to reduce (extend) the duration of working hours in a specific situation. This requirement must be fulfilled in cases that may harm the employer's interests⁵.

Precarious employment in Uzbekistan - implementation of labor activities in the informal sector, formalization of informal employment in developed countries taking into account the scale of illegal foreign labor migration, further strengthening of incentives for the able-bodied population to engage in entrepreneurial activities, at the same time, stable and effective new work it is advisable to take measures to drastically increase the organization of places.

⁴ Политические меры, направленные на сокращение неформальной занятости: Обзор международного опыта // <http://siteresources.worldbank.org/UKRAINE/UKRAINIANEXTN/Resources/4556801310372404373/PoliciestoReduceInformalEmploymentRUS.pdf>

⁵ Cardose P. et al. Precarious employment in Europe. Brussels: FEPS. 2014. – P.24.

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